

Crude and Essential Oil Content Composition of Indigenous Turkish Black and Brown Mustard Seeds

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Abstract

Brown and black mustard are two valuable species used as raw materials in the agro-industrial sector, particularly for their aromatic, medicinal, and potential bioenergy applications. This study aimed to evaluate the crude oil and essential oil contents and chemical compositions of six domestic mustard lines (three brown and three black mustard) cultivated in Türkiye. Fatty acid profiles of crude oils were analyzed using gas chromatography (GC), while essential oil components were determined via gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). Significant variability ($p < 0.01$) was observed among the lines for both essential oil and fatty acid composition. Among essential oil components, allyl isothiocyanate was the major compound across all lines, ranging from 69.44% in the Tekirdağ brown mustard line (J1) to 97.56% in the Türkiye-1 black mustard line (N1). Other prominent constituents included 2-butenitrile (0.93-1.93%), 3-butenyl isothiocyanate (0.20-2.22%), and, to a lesser extent, propyl isothiocyanate, 2-hexanol, and beta-phenyl ethyl isothiocyanate in specific lines. The maximum essential oil content (1.02%) was obtained from the Ankara black mustard line (N2), while the minimum (0.20%) was recorded in the İzmir brown mustard line (J2). Fatty acid analysis showed that erucic acid (C22:1) was the predominant fatty acid in black mustard lines (38.43-38.92%) compared to brown mustard lines (20.94-23.16%). In contrast, oleic acid (C18:1) content was higher in brown mustard-reaching up to 24.81% in the J2 than in black mustard lines (13.08-13.65%). Linoleic acid (C18:2) ranged from 15.01% to 22.01% across all lines. The highest crude oil content was observed in the J2 at 34.86%, whereas the lowest was found in the N1 at 27.19%. These results highlight the significant chemical diversity among domestic mustard lines in Türkiye and demonstrate their potential for use in breeding programs targeting industrial oil production and functional bioactive compounds.

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1. Introduction

*Brassic*as represent the second most widely cultivated oilseed crop globally, accounting for approximately 12% of total edible oil production and contributing protein-rich meal (35-40%) primarily used in animal feed (Raboanatahiry et al., 2021; Zheng and Liu, 2022). In addition to their nutritional value, *Brassica* species are also recognized for their aromatic, medicinal, and therapeutic properties (Darwesh, 2017; Nisar et al., 2018; Kayaçetin, 2020; Mayekar et al., 2021; Asaduzzaman et al., 2021). Mustard essential oil is characterized by a high content of allyl isothiocyanate, a volatile compound formed by the enzymatic hydrolysis of the glucosinolate sinigrin via myrosinase activity (Yu et al., 2003; Park et al., 2012). This compound is largely responsible for the distinctive pungent aroma and has been widely studied for its antimicrobial properties, making mustard seed powder a candidate for food preservation applications (Isshiki et al., 1992). Sinigrin is the predominant glucosinolate in black mustard (*Brassica nigra*), and its breakdown product allyl isothiocyanate plays a key role in both plant defense and biological activity (Divakaran and Babu, 2016; Miękus et al., 2020; Tarar et al., 2022). According to De Zoysa and Waisundara (2021), black mustard seeds are rich in various biologically active compounds, including oligosaccharides, amino acids, fatty acids, minerals, glucosinolates, phenolics, and anti-nutritional factors. These compounds have been associated with a range of pharmacological effects, such as anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antioxidant, antifungal, antibacterial, antithrombotic, anticonvulsant, and antidiabetic activities (Lakwani et al., 2022). Both brown and black mustard seeds contain small but significant amounts of essential oils (0.4-2.5%) and fixed oils (25-35%), with erucic acid comprising 30-40% of the total fatty acids in fixed oils (Kayaçetin et al., 2018; Kayaçetin et al., 2023; Alibrahem et al., 2025). Beyond total oil content, the qualitative composition of mustard oil, particularly the profiles of essential and non-essential fatty acids, is important for both

nutritional and industrial applications (Shyam et al., 2021). Major fatty acids of interest include oleic, linoleic, linolenic, erucic, and palmitic acids. Oils with a high proportion of monounsaturated fatty acids, such as oleic acid, are preferred for biodiesel production due to their oxidative stability and performance characteristics (Kayaçetin, 2023). However, low erucic acid mustard genotypes are preferred for edible use, as high levels of erucic acid are associated with potential cardiotoxicity. In contrast, industrial applications often benefit from high erucic acid content, particularly in the production of lubricants, plasticizers, cosmetics, hydraulic fluids, and biodiesel (Jham et al., 2009; Pandey et al., 2013; Kayaçetin and Khawar, 2023). The fatty acid profile of mustard seed oil is known to vary significantly depending on species, genotype, environmental conditions, and agronomic practices (Sharafi et al., 2015; Velasco et al., 2016, Rai et al., 2018). This compositional variability offers opportunities to tailor mustard varieties for specific end uses. Recent studies have also highlighted the diverse biological activities of Brassicaceae species, largely attributed to their glucosinolate contents and associated degradation products such as isothiocyanates (Maycotte, et al., 2025). The aim of the present study was to evaluate the crude oil content, essential oil content, and oil compositions of six indigenous mustard seed lines (*B. juncea* and *B. nigra*) selected from both exotic and local genetic resources in Türkiye. These lines have potential utility in breeding programs aimed at improving specific qualitative traits for nutritional and industrial applications.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material

This study was conducted using six pure lines of black mustard (*Brassica nigra* L.) and brown mustard (*Brassica juncea* L.). Their characteristics are summarized in Table 1. The mustard lines were provided by the Central Field Crops Research Institute (Ankara, Türkiye), and all laboratory analyses were performed at the Medicinal and Aromatic

Plants Laboratory of the Directorate of West mediterranean Agricultural Research Institute. Table 1 presents the origin of the brown and black mustard samples collected from different regions of Türkiye. Brown mustard lines were sourced from Tekirdağ (J1), İzmir (J2), and

Konya (J3), all exhibiting a uniform brown seed color. Similarly, black mustard lines originated from Türkiye-1 (N1), Ankara (N2), and Türkiye-2 (N3), and all displayed a consistent blackish-brown seed color (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of mustard pure lines used in the study

Common Name	Origin
Brown mustard	Tekirdağ / Türkiye (J1)
	İzmir / Türkiye (J2)
	Konya / Türkiye (J3)
Black mustard	Türkiye-1 (N1)
	Ankara / Türkiye (N2)
	Türkiye-2 (N3)

2.2. Essential oil extraction

Essential oil content was determined using a Clevenger-type hydrodistillation apparatus (İsotex, 98-IV-B). For each sample, 20 g of air-dried and ground seed material was weighed and transferred into a glass distillation flask. Approximately 200 mL of distilled water (10× the sample weight) was added, and the mixture was subjected to hydrodistillation for approximately two hours. The essential oil was collected in the graduated section of the apparatus, and its volume (in mL) was recorded. The essential oil yield was calculated as a percentage (v/w) based on the initial weight of the sample (Anonymous, 2011).

2.3. Essential oil composition analysis

Essential oil samples were diluted 1:100 in hexane before analysis. The chemical composition of the oils was determined using a Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry/Flame Ionization Detector (GC-MS/FID) system (Agilent 7890A GC, Agilent 5975C MSD) equipped with a capillary column (HP Innowax, 60.0 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm). The carrier gas was helium, with a constant flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. One microliter (1 μL) of the diluted sample was injected with a split ratio of 40:1. The injector temperature was set to 250 °C. The oven temperature program was as follows: 60 °C for 10 minutes, then increased to 220 °C at a rate of 4 °C/min, and held at 220 °C for an additional 10 minutes. The total run time was

60 minutes. The MS detector operated in the electron impact mode (70 eV), scanning in the 35-450 m/z range. Compound identification was based on WILEY7 and ADAMS OIL spectral libraries. Quantification was performed using the FID detector (Özek et al., 2010).

2.4. Crude oil content determination

Crude oil content was determined by Soxhlet extraction. Glass beakers used in the procedure were pre-dried in an oven to a constant weight, then tared. Approximately 5 g of finely ground seed sample was weighed and placed into a cellulose thimble, which was loaded into a Soxhlet extractor. A volume of 140 mL petroleum ether was used as the solvent. Following extraction, the solvent was evaporated, and the extraction flask was placed in an oven at 80 °C for one hour. After cooling in a desiccator, the crude oil content was calculated gravimetrically by the difference in beaker weight before and after extraction (Kayaçetin, 2023).

2.5. Crude oil composition analysis

The fatty acid composition of crude oil samples was determined following a transesterification procedure. Approximately 0.1 g of oil was accurately weighed into a glass vial, to which 0.2 mL of 2 M methanolic potassium hydroxide (KOH) was added. The mixture was vortexed thoroughly to ensure complete transesterification of triglycerides into fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES).

Subsequently, 2 mL of hexane was added, and the mixture was vortexed once again. After allowing the phases to separate for 5 minutes, 1 mL of the upper hexane layer containing the FAMES was carefully collected for gas chromatographic analysis. Samples were analyzed using an Agilent 7890A gas chromatography (GC) system coupled with both a flame ionization detector (FID) and a mass spectrometry detector (MSD, Agilent 5975C), operating in split injection mode (split ratio: 40:1) with an injection volume of 1 μ L. Chromatographic separation was carried out on an HP Innowax capillary column (60.0 m \times 0.25 mm i.d., 0.25 μ m film thickness). The column effluent was equally split (1:1) between the FID and MSD using a splitter. Helium served as the carrier gas at a constant flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. The injector temperature was maintained at 250 $^{\circ}$ C. The oven temperature program was as follows: initial temperature at 150 $^{\circ}$ C for 5 minutes, increased to 200 $^{\circ}$ C at 10 $^{\circ}$ C/min and held for 5 minutes, then further ramped to 250 $^{\circ}$ C at 5 $^{\circ}$ C/min and held for 10 minutes, resulting in a total run time of 30 minutes. Mass spectrometric detection was performed using electron impact ionization at 70 eV, with a scan range of m/z 35-450. Fatty acid components were identified by comparing mass spectra with the WILEY library and quantified based on FID peak areas, in accordance with the method described by Gölükçü et al. (2016). Statistical analysis: Data from the evaluated traits of black and brown mustard pure lines were statistically analyzed using JMP®13.2.1 (Statistical Analysis Software; SAS Institute Inc., North Carolina, US). Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine significant differences among the lines. Mean comparisons were conducted using the Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a significance level of 1% ($p < 0.01$).

3. Findings and Discussion

3.1. Findings

The essential oil and crude oil compositions identified through GC-MS and GC analyses are presented in Tables 2 and 3, respectively. All evaluated parameters exhibited statistically significant differences among the mustard seed lines ($p < 0.01$), indicating notable genetic variability.

3.1.1. Essential oil content and composition in indigenous black and brown mustard seeds

The essential oil composition of six mustard seed lines including three brown mustard (*Brassica juncea*) and three black mustard (*B. nigra*) lines demonstrated significant differences across all quantified compounds ($p < 0.01$). Among the brown mustard lines, J1 had the maximum proportion of 2-butenitrile (1.93%) but showed the minimum content of allyl isothiocyanate (69.44%) and lacked detectable levels of propyl isothiocyanate, 2-hexanol, and β -phenylethyl isothiocyanate. Conversely, J2 contained the minimum level of 2-butenitrile (0.93%) but exhibited a relatively high concentration of allyl isothiocyanate (82.86%), as well as detectable amounts of propyl isothiocyanate (0.13%) and β -phenylethyl isothiocyanate (0.57%). The J3 line was particularly rich in allyl isothiocyanate (94.50%) and had the maximum level of 3-butenyl isothiocyanate (2.22%) among brown mustard lines. J3 also contained measurable levels of propyl isothiocyanate (0.30%) and β -phenylethyl isothiocyanate (0.73%). Notably, none of the brown mustard lines exhibited detectable 2-hexanol (Table 2).

Table 2. Essential oil composition and essential oil content brown and black mustard lines

Species	Lines	2-Butenenitrile	Allyl isothiocyanate	3-Butenyl isothiocyanate	Propyl isothiocyanate	2-Hexanol	β -Phenylethyl isothiocyanate	Essential oil content (%)
Brown mustard	J1	1.93 ^a	69.44 ^c	0.75 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.38 ^c
	J2	0.93 ^d	82.86 ^d	1.14 ^b	0.13 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.57 ^b	0.20 ^d
	J3	1.20 ^c	94.50 ^c	2.22 ^a	0.30 ^a	0.00 ^b	0.73 ^a	0.62 ^b
Black mustard	N1	1.39 ^b	97.56 ^a	0.20 ^d	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^d	0.21 ^d
	N2	1.40 ^b	95.51 ^b	0.22 ^d	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^b	0.23 ^c	1.02 ^a
	N3	1.39 ^b	95.39 ^b	0.24 ^d	0.00 ^c	0.83 ^a	0.13 ^{cd}	0.60 ^b
ANOVA (p<0.01)		**	**	**	**	**	**	**

** p<0.01

In the black mustard group, N1 had the maximum concentration of allyl isothiocyanate across all lines (97.56%) but displayed minimal 3-butenyl isothiocyanate (0.20%) and only contained 2-butenitrile (1.39%) among the minor constituents. N2 presented similarly high allyl isothiocyanate (95.51%) and a slightly increased level of 3-butenyl isothiocyanate (0.22%). Importantly, it yielded the maximum essential oil content among all lines (1.02%). N3 was characterized by high allyl isothiocyanate content (95.39%) and moderate 3-butenyl isothiocyanate (0.24%). Uniquely, it was the only black mustard line containing 2-hexanol (0.83%) and also had detectable β -phenylethyl isothiocyanate (0.13%). In terms of total essential oil yield, black mustard lines generally outperformed their brown mustard counterparts. The maximum oil content was recorded in N2 (1.02%), followed by J3 (0.62%) and N3 (0.60%). On the other hand, the minimum yields were observed in J2

(0.20%) and N1 (0.21%) (Table 2). These findings reveal substantial variation in essential oil profiles and yields across lines, which appear to be both species- and line-dependent. Notably, allyl isothiocyanate was identified as the major volatile compound in both species, with considerably higher concentrations detected in *B. nigra* lines (up to 97.56%). This observation aligns with the known abundance of sinigrin, a shared glucosinolate precursor of AITC, in both species. The absence of this compound in *B. nigra* lines underscores chemotypic differentiation between the species. Overall, the superior essential oil yield of black mustard lines, especially N2, suggests that *B. nigra* may be more suitable for industrial essential oil extraction. These results collectively highlight the potential of both *B* species as sources of functionally valuable phytochemicals, with prospective applications in natural food preservation, nutraceuticals, and therapeutic formulations.

Table 3. Fatty acid composition and crude oil content of brown and black mustard lines

Species	Line	PA	SA	AA	BA	LA	PoA	OA	GA	EA	LA	α LA	EiA	CO
Brown Mustard	J1	2.76 ^b	1.52 ^a	1.07 ^b	0.61 ^c	0.56 ^{ab}	0.16 ^b	24.12 ^b	12.75 ^b	23.16 ^a	20.58 ^b	11.73 ^{sd}	0.75 ^b	34.42 ^b
	J2	3.10 ^a	1.50 ^a	1.04 ^b	0.47 ^d	0.49 ^{bc}	0.17 ^b	24.81 ^a	13.40 ^a	20.94 ^d	20.87 ^b	12.22 ^{bc}	0.82 ^b	34.86 ^a
	J3	3.13 ^a	1.36 ^{ab}	0.98 ^b	0.58 ^c	0.58 ^{ab}	0.16 ^b	23.68 ^b	12.85 ^b	22.24 ^c	22.01 ^a	11.38 ^d	0.71 ^b	27.88 ^d
Black Mustard	N1	2.86 ^b	1.37 ^{ab}	1.40 ^a	1.61 ^a	0.51 ^{bc}	0.15 ^b	13.65 ^c	10.43 ^c	38.43 ^a	15.01 ^d	12.82 ^a	0.98 ^a	27.19 ^c
	N2	2.88 ^b	1.35 ^{ab}	1.33 ^a	1.38 ^b	0.43 ^c	0.23 ^a	13.08 ^d	10.63 ^c	38.92 ^a	15.57 ^c	12.61 ^b	1.01 ^a	27.34 ^c
	N3	2.88 ^b	1.09 ^b	1.38 ^a	1.42 ^b	0.65 ^a	0.20 ^{ab}	13.65 ^c	10.79 ^c	38.56 ^a	15.75 ^c	12.06 ^{bc}	1.02 ^a	28.57 ^c
ANOVA (p<0.01)		**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**

** p < 0.01. PA: Palmitic Acid (C16:0); SA: Stearic Acid (C18:0); AA: Arachidic Acid (C20:0); BA: Behenic Acid (C22:0); LA: Lignoceric Acid (C24:0); PoA: Palmitoleic Acid (C16:1); OA: Oleic Acid (C18:1); GA: Gondoic Acid (C20:1); EA: Erucic Acid (C22:1); LA: Linoleic Acid (C18:2); Ala: α -Linolenic Acid (C18:3n3); EA: Eicosadienoic Acid (C20:2); CO: Crude Oil (%)

3.1.2. Crude oil and fatty acid composition of indigenous black and brown mustard seeds

The fatty acid profiles and crude oil contents of the indigenous *B juncea* (brown mustard) and *B nigra* (black mustard) lines exhibited considerable variation (Table 3). Among the brown mustard lines, J1 had a crude oil content of 34.42% and contained the following saturated fatty acids: 2.76% palmitic acid (C16:0), 1.52% stearic acid (C18:0), 1.07% arachidic acid (C20:0), 0.61% behenic acid (C22:0), and 0.56% lignoceric acid (C24:0). Its monounsaturated fatty acids included 0.16% palmitoleic acid (C16:1), 24.12% oleic acid (C18:1), and 12.75% gondoic acid (C20:1). Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs) were represented by 23.16% erucic acid (C22:1), 20.58% linoleic acid (C18:2), 11.73% α -linolenic acid (C18:3n3), and 0.75% 11.13-eicosadienoic acid. J2 exhibited the maximum crude oil content among brown mustard lines (34.86%). Its saturated fatty acids included 3.10% palmitic, 1.50% stearic, 1.04% arachidic, 0.47% behenic, and 0.49% lignoceric acids. Monounsaturated fatty acids were 0.17% palmitoleic, 24.81% oleic, and 13.40% gondoic acids. The PUFA profile consisted of 20.94% erucic, 20.87% linoleic, 12.22% α -linolenic, and 0.82% 11.13-eicosadienoic acids. J3, which had the minimum oil content among brown mustard lines (27.88%), contained slightly higher palmitic acid (3.13%) but lower stearic (1.36%) and arachidic acids (0.98%). It included 0.16% palmitoleic, 23.68% oleic, and 12.85% gondoic acids as monounsaturated fats. Polyunsaturated fatty acids were measured at 22.24% erucic, 22.01% linoleic, 11.38% α -linolenic, and 0.71% 11.13-eicosadienoic acid. Among the black mustard lines, N1 showed a crude oil content of 27.19% and had 2.86% palmitic, 1.37% stearic, 1.40% arachidic, 1.61% behenic, and 0.51% lignoceric acids as saturated fats. Monounsaturated fatty acids included 0.15% palmitoleic, 13.65% oleic, and 10.43% gondoic acids. The PUFA composition was dominated by 38.43% erucic acid, along with 15.01% linoleic, 12.82% α -linolenic, and

0.98% 11.13-eicosadienoic acid. N2 had a similar fatty acid profile, with saturated fats comprising 2.88% palmitic, 1.35% stearic, 1.33% arachidic, 1.38% behenic, and 0.43% lignoceric acids. It contained 0.23% palmitoleic, 13.08% oleic, and 10.63% gondoic acids. Its polyunsaturated fatty acids were 38.92% erucic, 15.57% linoleic, 12.61% α -linolenic, and 1.01% 11.13-eicosadienoic acid. The crude oil content was 27.34%. N3 exhibited the maximum crude oil content among black mustard lines (28.57%) and contained 2.88% palmitic, 1.09% stearic, 1.38% arachidic, 1.42% behenic, and 0.65% lignoceric acids. Its monounsaturated fatty acids were measured at 0.20% palmitoleic, 13.65% oleic, and 10.79% gondoic acids, while its polyunsaturated fatty acid composition consisted of 38.56% erucic, 15.75% linoleic, 12.06% α -linolenic, and 1.02% 11.13-eicosadienoic acid.

3.2. Discussion

3.2.1. Essential oil content and composition of indigenous black and brown mustard seeds

The essential oil content and composition of six mustard seed lines, comprising both *B. juncea* (brown mustard) and *B. nigra* (black mustard), showed statistically significant variation across all analyzed compounds ($p < 0.01$) (Table 2). Allyl isothiocyanate (AITC) was identified as the predominant volatile constituent in all lines, though its concentration varied markedly between lines and species. The maximum AITC content was recorded in the black mustard line N1 (97.56%), followed closely by N2 (95.51%) and N3 (95.39%). Conversely, brown mustard lines generally exhibited lower AITC levels, with J1 presenting the minimum (69.44%) and J3 the maximum content within this group (94.50%). β -Phenylethyl isothiocyanate (β -PEITC), a bioactive compound with well-documented anticancer properties (Peng et al., 2014), was exclusively detected in brown mustard lines, particularly in J2 (0.57%) and J3 (0.73%), and was absent or negligible in black mustard genotypes. This finding suggests a

genotypic specificity in the biosynthetic pathways responsible for this compound. Additionally, 3-butenyl isothiocyanate and propyl isothiocyanate were present at relatively low concentrations, contributing to chemical diversity, with J3 again exhibiting the maximum levels among brown mustard lines. Notably, 2-hexanol, a minor alcohol compound, was detected solely in black mustard line N3 (0.83%), further differentiating the chemical profiles of the species. Regarding total essential oil yield, black mustard lines generally outperformed their brown mustard counterparts. The maximum essential oil content was observed in the Ankara black mustard line N2 (1.02%), followed by the Konya brown mustard line J3 (0.62%) and the Türkiye-2 black mustard line N3 (0.60%). In contrast, the lowest yields were recorded in the İzmir brown mustard line J2 (0.20%) and the Türkiye-1 black mustard line N1 (0.21%). This variation among lines indicates that environmental adaptation, genetic background, and glucosinolate biosynthesis pathways collectively influence essential oil accumulation (Fahey et al., 2001; Sinha et al., 2007). These results corroborate previous studies reporting sinigrin the primary glucosinolate precursor of allyl isothiocyanate (AITC) as the dominant metabolite in *Brassica* species. Elevated AITC levels in *B. nigra* lines reinforce their potential utility in industrial sectors requiring potent antimicrobial, insecticidal, and flavor-enhancing compounds (Liener, 2012; Mazumder et al., 2016). Additionally, the strong volatility and bioactivity of AITC have been associated with enhanced defense responses in *Brassicaceae* plants, which may partially explain the higher essential oil production observed in black mustard lines (Akhtar and Khan, 2024; Barea-Ramos et al., 2024). Furthermore, several studies have emphasized the role of agroecological conditions, sulfur nutrition, and enzymatic myrosinase activity in regulating glucosinolate hydrolysis and AITC formation (Angelino et al., 2015; Sharma et al., 2025). Incorporating these physiological and biochemical factors into breeding programs may therefore enhance the stability and yield

of desirable bioactive compounds in mustard. Overall, the superior AITC-rich profile of *B. nigra* lines strengthens their suitability for food preservation, natural pesticide formulations, and pharmaceutical applications (Mazumder et al., 2016). Collectively, the observed variation in essential oil constituents indicates a strong genotypic influence on volatile profiles, likely shaped by genetic and environmental factors. This diversity underscores the potential for targeted exploitation in functional foods, phytopharmaceuticals, and biopesticides.

3.2.2. Crude oil and fatty acid composition of indigenous black and brown mustard seeds

The fatty acid profiles and crude oil contents of the six mustard seed lines also demonstrated significant differences ($p < 0.01$) (Table 3). Brown mustard lines generally exhibited higher levels of monounsaturated fatty acids (MUFA), especially oleic acid (C18:1), ranging from 23.68% (J3) to 24.81% (J2). In contrast, black mustard lines contained markedly elevated erucic acid (C22:1) levels, between 38.43% and 38.92%, compared to 20.94-23.16% in brown mustard. These findings align with prior reports indicating that *B. nigra* typically accumulates higher erucic acid contents (Kaur et al., 2022; Kayaçetin, 2023). Polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFA), primarily linoleic (C18:2) and α -linolenic acid (C18:3n3), were more abundant in brown mustard lines. For instance, J3 exhibited the maximum linoleic acid content (22.01%) alongside substantial α -linolenic acid (11.38%), reflecting a nutritionally favorable and more balanced fatty acid profile. While black mustard lines were richer in erucic acid, they also maintained moderate levels of linoleic (15.01-15.75%) and α -linolenic acid (12.06-12.82%), indicating some nutritional relevance. Saturated fatty acid (SFA) contents, including palmitic, stearic, arachidic, and behenic acids, were comparable across all lines, with only minor variation observed in lignoceric and palmitoleic acids. Regarding crude oil yield, brown mustard lines J2 (34.86%) and J1 (34.42%) exhibited the maximum contents. In comparison, black mustard lines demonstrated slightly lower

crude oil percentages (27.19-28.57%). This disparity suggests a possible trade-off between oil yield and erucic acid accumulation, whereby brown mustard lines offer superior oil quantity and a healthier fatty acid profile, while black mustard lines provide compositions better suited for industrial applications (Jham et al., 2009; Singh et al., 2014; Kayaçetin et al., 2018; Kayaçetin, 2025).

4. Conclusion

This study revealed significant genetic and chemical diversity among six indigenous mustard seed lines (three *B. juncea* and three *B. nigra*) cultivated in Ankara, Türkiye, particularly in terms of crude oil and essential oil contents and compositions. While black mustard excels in essential oil yield and AITC concentration, making it a promising candidate for industrial and phytochemical exploitation, brown mustard provides superior nutritional oil quality due to higher MUFA and PUFA contents and lower erucic acid levels. These results provide a strong foundation for the valorization of mustard germplasm in both food-grade and non-edible oil markets. Among the lines, brown mustard line J2 stood out with the maximum crude oil content (34.86%) and a favorable fatty acid profile for dietary use, while black mustard line N2 exhibited the maximum essential oil content (1.02%) with a rich isothiocyanate profile suitable for antimicrobial or aromatic applications. The observed variability across lines highlights the potential of Turkish mustard germplasm as a valuable source for breeding programs aimed at enhancing specific oil traits for diverse end-uses. These results support the strategic development and valorization of mustard cultivars based on intended industrial or nutritional applications and emphasize the importance of conserving and utilizing local genetic resources to meet future agri-food and bio-based industry demands.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved

the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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